

Everything we (think we) know about Narrative CVs (NCVs)

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*This is one of three briefings sharing key insights from our work on NCV implementation. This edition is for **meta-researchers studying NCV implementation** for funding allocation, hiring, promotion, or other purposes. The other briefings target organisations considering NCV implementation and organisations already implementing NCVs.*

Overview

This briefing presents insights and recommendations for meta-researchers studying NCV implementation, based on a review of publicly available documents and stakeholder engagement in targeted interviews, focus groups, and co-creative workshops.

We explored three questions:

1. What do / don't we know about user reactions to NCVs?
2. What do / don't we know about NCV implementation outcomes?
3. What do / don't we know about the effectiveness of guidance and support?

Key insights

Our work concludes on the following answers to these questions:

- 1. User reactions:** The evidence base on NCV implementation primarily explores user experiences in the context of funding grant applications and evaluations. Studies examine acceptance of the NCV, comparisons with traditional formats, and the opportunities and challenges encountered by both applicants and reviewers. **Knowledge of NCV use for hiring, appointment or promotion contexts in universities remains limited, even though implementation is expected to be more complex in those contexts. There is also little understanding of how experiences differ across NCV formats, such as those relying on open versus directional prompting.**
- 2. Outcomes:** The intended outcomes of NCV implementation are often insufficiently defined, making it difficult to collect robust evidence on whether they have been achieved. Evaluations of user experience capture perceptions of the format's potential to create space for more diverse contributions and to enable recognition of non-traditional career paths, but **little work assesses whether this results in selection of individuals with different profiles and ultimately to improvements in research quality and impact. Although bias is a recurring theme in user feedback, it has barely been addressed in research.** The lack of a clear definition of bias in research evaluation, minimal evidence of bias linked to traditional researcher CVs, and uncertainty about whether bias can be attributed to the CV rather than other elements of assessment processes make this a challenging area to explore.
- 3. Guidance and support:** While guidance for applicants is widely available from funders and institutions, resources for reviewers are often not public or easy to access. User evaluations, including those focused on caregivers and underrepresented researchers, highlight measures that could better support both applicants and reviewers. **Areas needing further attention include understanding how varying levels of support affect applicant success and how reviewers respond to different support, guidance and training mechanisms – in part to learn from what works and what doesn't.**

Recommendations for meta-researchers studying NCV implementation

Based on the full review, we recommend that meta-researchers studying NCVs:

- **Assess prerequisites before evaluating outcomes** – Achieving intended outcomes from NCV implementation depends on a range of factors, including clearly defining intended goals, alignment between evaluation practices and NCV principles, and reinforcement of intended use in panel settings. Evaluations that aim to assess whether outcomes are being achieved but overlook these conditions, risk producing misleading results.
- **Include Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS) researchers in both study design and participation** – Ongoing underrepresentation of AHSS researchers both as participants in NCV implementation studies and as research designers leads to terminology and concepts used in NCVs not being adapted to AHSS. If NCVs are to be used across disciplines, their inclusion is essential.
- **Collaborate with implementing organisations to generate meaningful and comparable data** – Workshops revealed that the greatest value lies in access to live panel observations, evaluation data, longitudinal and cross-organisational datasets, and data on institutional permeation and adoption. Direct engagement with organisations is key to securing access to such data sets.
- **Focus future research on identified blind spots** – These include: i) conceptual work to define key analytical but underspecified concepts such as research culture, excellence, bias, fairness, inclusivity, etc.; ii) understanding NCV use in institutional contexts e.g. for hiring, tenure and promotion; iii) understanding how NCVs are used by assessors, e.g. through observational or eye-tracking studies; iv) comparative experiments between traditional and NCVs in relation to bias, subjectivity, verifiability of claims and use of AI or between NCV format types in relation to their effectiveness to achieve outcomes; v) evaluation of longer-term outcomes including impact on research quality.
- Questions remain about **how much evidence is needed to support wider NCV adoption, and what level of resource is appropriate to evaluate success**. While our review does not answer these questions, researchers (and funders) may wish to consider them when prioritising future work.

Key opportunity / challenge

Opportunity: While user experience of NCVs has been well studied, there are opportunities to increase our understanding of NCV effectiveness in achieving outcomes and to use NCV studies for examining academic culture change.

Challenge: Reliable evidence on the effectiveness of NCVs will need to start from better specification of underpinning concepts; be mindful of the various factors that play into implementation success, and find ways to mitigate challenges such as small sample sizes.

Further background

Several organisations have, over the past decade, piloted and implemented a new academic CV format known as the 'Narrative CV' (NCV), which emphasises narrative over itemised lists and allows users to expand beyond the typical career and output milestones usually included in CVs. This shift was driven by concerns about the excessive focus on quantitative criteria in review and hiring panels, often seen to encourage perverse incentives. It is also considered an important tool for virtue signalling towards better research culture.

The format was introduced with a range of intended outcomes in mind and has since been evaluated through studies focused mainly on user acceptance and experience, as well as changes in CV use and evaluation practices as a result of NCV introduction.

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Annex - Overview of findings for intended outcomes

Outcomes in this overview were consolidated across the studies considered in our review, alongside outcomes captured in the Joint Funders Group & Alternative Uses Group (2023) *Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI)-like narrative CV: Shared Evaluation Framework (2.0)*. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8060614>

<p>Streamlining and simplification</p>	<p>Several studies recommend further alignment of NCVs within and between organisations, while noting that this should mean requesting relevant information in the same format, rather than blanket standardisation.</p> <p>Survey data on the time and difficulty of writing or reviewing NCVs show mixed experiences. Applicants often spend more time preparing their first NCV, and reviewers initially find them harder to assess than traditional CVs.</p>
<p>Streamlining and simplification</p>	<p>Several studies show that a broader range of outputs and contributions is included in NCVs and is being considered in evaluations, and data across studies confirms users agree the format supports this goal.</p> <p>However, there is limited evidence that this leads to more diverse funding outcomes, at least in the short term. A few studies offer anecdotal examples suggesting the format may benefit a small group of individuals who previously might have been excluded.</p>
<p>Reducing barriers across sectors and disciplines</p>	<p>Data across studies confirms users agree the format supports the goal of reducing barriers across sectors and disciplines.</p> <p>Some studies suggest NCVs help shift perceptions of irregular career paths, but workshop participants noted that the NCV, while offering space for the description of competencies, cannot resolve the inherent misalignment between outputs-focused evaluation in academia and competency-focused evaluation in other sectors.</p>
<p>Reducing bias / Supporting EDI</p>	<p>Many studies raise concerns that NCVs may introduce bias, disadvantaging certain groups (e.g. gender, minoritised, English level, writing skills, confidence, institutional support, seniority). One study notes a missed opportunity for NCVs to better support caregivers.</p> <p>Evidence on how bias plays out is limited; one text analysis found language differences by demographics as well as positively evaluated NCVs having distinct language features.</p> <p>Another study found promotional language is rare, and positive language is occasional and does not result in a selection advantage. A challenge consists of a lack of clear definitions of bias in research evaluation more generally, and to establish the extent to which bias can be attributed to NCVs specifically rather than systemic effects.</p>
<p>Driving mindset change and better research culture</p>	<p>A few studies suggest a mindset shift is happening; applicants reflect differently on achievements, and reviewers reconsider the complexity of excellence and rethink how it is assessed, especially when supported throughout the evaluation process. At the same time, several studies show reviewers often continue to rely on traditional, publication-based indicators, with feedback highlighting difficulty evaluating without them.</p> <p>Several studies suggest that introducing NCVs as a standalone intervention is unlikely to lead to meaningful shifts in mindset and culture. Achieving such change requires a broader alignment of other evaluation and organisational measures moving in the same direction.</p>